

Novel Frontier Detection and Optimisation for Scalable Autonomous Exploration

Aymon Hussain
aymonh2017@gmail.com

Abstract—Autonomous exploration must be fast, scalable, and complete, yet popular frontier based methods either scan exhaustively (e.g., classical BFS/wavefront) or restrict search locally (e.g., Naïve Active Area, Expanding Wavefront), leading to high computational cost or missed opportunities as maps grow. We propose a hybrid framework that introduces a grid-tree frontier detector that hierarchically focuses search and parallelises evaluation to avoid re-scanning, adds a CNN-based learned detector for rapid frontier inference, and employs Bayesian optimisation to auto-tune goal-selection weights. In simulation across various maps, the grid tree method achieves up to 3.8× lower per-cycle computation than a naive baseline while preserving completeness; the learned detector is faster still with minor completeness loss. By reducing frontier detection overhead and automating parameter tuning, the framework addresses the efficiency–completeness gap in frontier exploration.

Index Terms—Autonomous exploration, Frontier detection, Machine learning, Bayesian optimization, Mobile robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous exploration is a necessity for robots tasked with navigating and operating in an unknown environment for tasks such as search and rescue, planetary exploration and autonomous warehousing [1]. Thus, the challenge lies in enabling robots to explore efficiently, mapping their surroundings while minimising time, resource consumption and computational overhead. A popular and widely used solution is frontier based exploration [2], which attempts to maximise exploration by guiding robots to explore “frontiers”, boundaries between known and unknown space. While effective, existing frontier based approaches often experience challenges in scalability and computational efficiency [12]. These limitations hinder the real-world applicability of these methods. For example, traditional frontier detection methods like the Wavefront Frontier Detector can become computationally expensive as the environment’s size increases thus leading to slower exploration times [2].

The aim of this paper is to create and develop a robust frontier based exploration algorithm that seeks to address these challenges. Using advanced techniques the implementations in this paper aim to enhance a robot’s ability to map and navigate unknown territories consistently.

The contents of this paper include implementing novel solutions for frontier based exploration with a simulated robot equipped with lidar sensors that can map, navigate and plan in an unknown environment. Evaluating the system’s performance in varying levels of environments. Analysing the limitations and failure cases to identify potential improvements.

Although frontier based exploration has been widely studied, many solutions trade-off between speed and completeness. This paper, in contrast, focuses on prioritising the implementation’s completeness and speed in realistic settings, where scalability and complexity pose additional challenges.

A. Contributions

The contributions of this paper are as follows:

- Using a machine learning object detector model for frontier detection as a solution for frontier based exploration.
- A novel tree grid structure to represent and search a map for frontier detection as a second non-ML solution.
- Using Bayesian optimisation for weight tuning to find optimal behaviour for goal selection.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Previous Frontier Based Exploration Implementations

The concept of frontier-based exploration was originally proposed and implemented by Brian Yamauchi [3]. The frontier detection algorithm uses an exhaustive Breadth First Search on the entire occupancy grid [4] to find frontiers and another BFS to cluster frontiers into centroids (a collection of neighbouring frontiers between two boundaries of occupied-space) and the robot drives to the closest one [3].

There have been many variations to improve the speed of the naive approach to frontier based exploration.

Popular variations include:

- Naive Active Area Frontier Detector (only performs scans in the regions currently covered by sensors) [5]
- Wavefront Frontier Detector (scans starting from the robot’s current position, expanding outward through known free space until it hits unknown territory) [5]
- Frontier Tracing Frontier Detector (tracing scan endpoints from sensors like LiDAR to find boundaries between known and unknown space) [5]

Previous frontier detectors [2], [5] scan exhaustively or limit scope, but none parallelise cell evaluation as we do.

B. Bayesian Optimisation

Bayesian optimisation is a strategy used for finding the minimum or maximum of functions that are typically expensive to evaluate that are often referred to as black-box functions [8]. It is useful in settings where each function evaluation, in our case simulation run, is time-consuming. Instead of attempting to directly optimise expensive functions

relying on gradient information or exhaustive search, Bayesian optimisation constructs a probabilistic surrogate model, in our case a Gaussian process, that approximates the objective function based on a limited number of observed points to select promising candidates for evaluation. This model provides both a prediction and an estimate of uncertainty for unseen points.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Grid Tree Based Frontier Detection

This is a novel algorithm designed to improve upon naive frontier detection by avoiding scanning the entire occupancy grid on every iteration. The algorithm works as follows:

The algorithm incrementally builds a tree of nodes covering free space: starting at the robot’s position, it expands outward in a grid pattern (children in a grid around each parent node), but only parent nodes within free space generate children as seen in Fig 6. Each node at creation and its parent node is marked as “unsearched”. Nodes that are flagged as unsearched are collected in a set. Frontier detection then happens by evaluating cells within each unsearched node’s boundaries defined by the grid size. Nodes that do not contain frontiers are marked as searched ensuring subsequent scans focus only on regions that contain frontier boundaries, the method avoids re-scanning the entire map on each iteration. We use parallel processing [10] to evaluate frontier cells within each unsearched node square concurrently, this yields a significant speedup. Finally, clustering (DBSCAN) [11] is applied to group the identified frontier cells and compute centroids. A flowchart overview of the algorithm can be seen in Fig 1.

B. Learned Image Detection

This is a machine learning approach to frontier detection. It is able to combine many of the traditional steps however, it sacrifices accuracy for speed and approximation. The rationale is that a neural network can learn to directly identify the contour of unexplored regions on a map without exhaustive cell-by-cell search potentially improving speed and robustness to noise under certain conditions. The algorithm works as follows:

First we load the YOLOv11 CNN model [6] with its weights and set it to use the CPU, this is done to make the comparison between the two approaches fairer. Next the occupancy grid is converted into an image with each cell value corresponding to a particular colour, free space is white, occupied space is black and unknown space is grey. This image is then passed to the image detector model for inference. This returns a structure containing results with all the bounding box data. We parse the structure for all the bounding box positions and calculate the areas and use these as centroids. The output inference can be seen in Fig 2.

We trained the image detector was by collecting training material using the data collection module. Then, using annotation software, 100 images were manually annotated, labeling every frontier region on each image. The model was then trained on this set of images using a Google Colab A100 GPU with a normal training split of 80-10-10 training, validation and

Fig. 1: Overview of Grid Tree Frontier Algorithm

Fig. 2: Output of YOLO CNN Model

testing data, achieving a mAP50 of 0.85. We then exported our trained model’s best weights as a Pytorch file.

C. Bayesian Optimisation Subsystem

A novel part of our system’s design is the use of Bayesian optimisation to automatically tune the goal selection weights for optimal exploration efficiency. Rather than manually guessing these weights, we treated them as hyper-parameters to be optimised with respect to a performance metric ; area covered per unit of time. The exploration node computes a performance metric at every cycle. Our approach uses Bayesian optimisation with a Gaussian Process modeling the objective, to find weight values (w_1, w_2, w_3 with ranges of 0-10 and priors of 1) that maximise this metric. The implementation uses the scikit-optimize library’s `gp_minimize` function. We set up a routine that performs repeated simulation trials. In each trial, it randomly selects one of several simulated environments and launches the entire exploration system with a candidate set of weights. It lets the robot explore for a fixed duration in that world, then records the performance metric that is published by the exploration node at the end of the run. The Bayesian optimiser uses these observations to suggest a new set of weights for the next run, aiming to improve the metric. This process was integrated by automatically launching ROS2 nodes through subprocess calls in the Python script.

In an academic context, this use of Bayesian optimisation is noteworthy as it treats the exploration algorithm itself as an optimisation problem. Our design therefore includes not just static logic, but a feedback loop. The final exploration controller uses the optimised weights by default but they are configurable for different use cases.

The incorporation of a weighted decision mechanism with learned parameters is what gives the exploration subsystem

a degree of intelligence beyond naive nearest frontier approaches.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. System Testing

System testing was done by deploying the complete exploration system in simulated environments that emulate real-world conditions. The tool used was Gazebo in which a TurtleBot4 robot was placed in various pre-built worlds. These worlds include a **Maze** (a network of narrow corridors), a **Depot** (a medium sized cluttered space with shelves and various obstacles) and a **Warehouse** (a large open space with various large shelves and storages). The objective of the system testing was to validate overall functionality and measure performance in these environments. Ensuring the system meets its design goals when faced with real-world complexities.

Throughout the system tests, minimal manual intervention was needed (about 3 times for image detector approach), the exploration was fully autonomous otherwise. The robot did not get stuck in any infinite loops or exhibit unsafe behaviour. The results from system testing provided strong evidence that the exploration system functions well in realistic settings and can handle different types of environments.

V. RESULTS

A. Performance Testing

This section presents a comprehensive performance evaluation of the system. Experiments were conducted in the previously mentioned environments to compare how each method performs under varying conditions to a baseline naive frontier detector. We chose this baseline over other approaches as they use localised/limited scans instead of holistic searches. The evaluation focuses on key metrics of efficiency and coverage, including computation time, search space size per detection cycle and exploration rate with and without Bayesian optimisation. Formal analysis and comparisons are provided to explain why a certain method performed better under specific conditions.

1) *Evaluation Metrics and Setup:* To assess the system’s performance, the following metrics were measured for each approach and environment:

- **Computation time per Frontier Detection Cycle:** The time in second taken for the algorithm to identify all current frontier points in one cycle. As the image detector combines multiple steps we use the inference time as a comparison. This reflects the real time computational overhead. Lower times indicate a more efficient algorithm that can run at a higher frequency.
- **Number of Occupancy Grid Cells Evaluated per Cycle:** The amount of cells that each method examines on every cycle. This gauges algorithmic efficiency as a lower count means a more focused approach.
- **Area Explored per Unit Time:** This is the exploration coverage rate, computed as total new area discovered

divided by exploration time. This is a holistic metric of how quickly the robot covers unknown space, affected by both the frontier detection strategy and exploration weighting strategy.

The naive frontier detection approach was integrated into the same exploration framework for a fair comparison. In all cases, a TurtleBot4 robot using the SLAM Toolbox was used. Simulations were run in all three environments using pre-determined robot paths to ensure a fair comparison of the different approaches' efficiency. Static map tests were also done to compute the average of each approach as well.

2) *Performance*: The performance of the **Naive Frontier Detectors** computation time in and total cell evaluation were plotted in Fig 4. As we expect, we see a linear behaviour between increasing map size and computation time/cells evaluated. As the map grows the naive detector detects the entire connecting region for frontiers, much of which may be unchanged from previous cycle. This redundant work resulted in computation times that quickly exceeded the "real time" maximum threshold of a second. The maze environment is a relatively small map with a complex layout and thus less of the map is revealed during exploration and we still see sub-optimal performance from the baseline. Grid Tree Based Frontier Detectors following the same path of the baseline we observe a sub-linear relationship between increasing map size and computation time/cells evaluated. The grid tree based approach proved advantageous in the maze environment because of its region focused search with the grid size set to 20 and the number of subprocess workers set to 12. After a child node is created in a newly found region it is only scanned once and subsequently scanned after only if a frontier is found within the nodes region. This can be seen in the spikes on the graphs where large amounts of new areas are discovered thus causing a spike in the number of cells evaluated in that cycle, which then drops back down after those new nodes are flagged as searched. This behaviour coupled with the fact that the small, complex layout of the map means new area is mostly discovered along the pre-determined path of the robot. By the end of exploration we can see an increase of computation performance by a factor of approximately 3.8 and the total amount of cells evaluated in the last pass by a factor of approximately 4. **Image Detector Frontier Detector** boasted the best performance in this scenario. A non-linear relationship was also observed between increasing map size and computation time; however, the trend was linear for the number of cells evaluated. The computation time remained fairly constant as the map grew, with only an initial anomalous value most likely due to some overhead. The high linear cells evaluated graph is due to passing the whole map as a full-resolution image to the model and thus all cells are "evaluated" per pass. Due to the complexity of the map when the inference output shows that a few small centroids were missed; however, these are insubstantial since larger nearby centroids were detected (so those areas would still be explored).

3) *Scalability and Completeness*: Tests were also conducted to see how each approach scales, and to evaluate each

Fig. 3: Computation and Cell Evaluation of Each Strategy in Maze Following Pre-Determined Path

method's completeness. The assumption that the Naive method is complete is based off previous academic papers [2] and thus we use the total amount of centroids detected with it as the baseline. Using the largest map Warehouse we measure each approach on a fixed amount area by simply running each algorithm after manually exploring a portion of the warehouse map. Each detector will run for 20 cycles and the total amount of centroids will be recorded and computation time.

In a large partially explored map (314k cells), naive evaluated 99.8% of cells and found 13 centroids in 5.9s (Fig 3), while grid tree evaluated 73.31% on the first pass then 18.29% on subsequent passes, finding the same 13 centroids in 0.8075s on average per cycle. The image method evaluated 100% of cells (by converting to image) but still only took 0.109s, finding 9/13 centroids, missing a few small ones.

Even though the grid tree algorithm scanned fewer cells after the first cycle, it still detected the 13 centroids matching the count from the baseline. This implies that the grid tree based detector's sampling of the map was sufficient to identify the same frontiers as the exhaustive approach, albeit by focusing only on nodes containing region boundaries and newly discovered areas rather than the entire map at every cycle. Hence the method appears to preserve completeness in the sense of detecting all major frontier clusters while substantially cutting down on redundant cell checks. When contrasted with the Naive or grid tree based method, the image detector method clearly displays much lower computation times than the Naive in this context, even though both evaluate the entire map on each pass. The difference in the efficiency of image based inference compared to Naive cell by cell logic. However, it leverages a deep learning framework that is mostly written

Fig. 4: Computation and Cell Evaluation of Each Strategy in Largely Discovered Static Warehouse Map

in C++ for performance-critical components. This calls into question whether the image-based method is truly comparable to the other two methods, which are written entirely in Python. We would see a significant improvement in performance if the other two methods were written in C++ and thus would be a fairer comparison. Overall these results highlight the distinct trade-off between the three methods. The naive method is slow but complete, whereas the image detector favours speed over completeness, and the grid tree based method sits in the middle of these offering both moderate speed and being complete.

4) *Grid Tree Based Frontier Detector Grid Size Performance*: In this section we investigated how the grid size parameter affects the performance and quality of map representation produced by the grid tree based approach. Using a partially discovered Maze map for its complex layout we tested various grid sizes and observed their effects on computation time, cell evaluation and map representation.

We evaluated grid sizes 6, 10, 20 in the maze. All detected the same 21 of centroids, indicating no loss of completeness. The smaller grid (6) scanned only 55.21% of the total cells in the first cycle and 10.03% thereafter, whereas the larger grid (20) scanned 82.04% initially and 27.43% thereafter. However, overhead of managing many small nodes made the small-grid size slower (first cycle 1.07s at grid=6 vs 0.78s at grid=20; subsequent 0.68s vs 0.65s). Thus, a moderate grid size (10) gave the best balance (initial 0.85s, then 0.65s) by reducing node count without scanning too many extra cells. We conclude that a grid size between 10 and 20 is near optimal for performance.

Fig. 5: Computation and Cell Evaluation of Each Grid Size for Maze

B. Bayesian Optimisation Improvements

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of the Bayesian optimisation subsystem. Multiple independent runs of this subsystem were performed to tune the weights used in the goal selection cost function to maximise exploration. The following table contains the results of these runs:

TABLE I: Results from various Bayesian Optimisation runs

Run	w1	w2	w3	Best Performance
run1 (30 trials)	0.412047	0.0	0.0	5.09376
run2 (30 trials)	10.0	10.0	0.0	1.42804
run3 (30 trials)	3.90108	8.49354	9.11890	-0.0
run4 (30 trials)	4.16821	7.17104	4.27177	6.21557
run5 (100 trials)	9.65043	5.92627	8.79552	6.60319

Key Observations

Run 1 assigns a very small weight to w1 (euclidean distance of the robot to the centroid) while leaving w2 (angular difference of the robot relative to the centroid) and w3 (centroid size) at zero. This simplistic configuration focusing solely on the euclidean distance between the robot and the goal, resulted in a moderate performance metric of 5.0938 (area covered per second). Although straightforward it ignores additional criteria missing out on nuanced information about centroids.

Run 2 explores the opposite extreme by maximising both w1 and w2 while keeping w3 at zero. This approach yielded a considerably lower performance, suggesting that heavily penalising centroids further away and a higher angular difference can adversely affect the overall goal selection.

Run 3 is a failed run as the system was mistakenly set to minimise exploration.

Run 4 demonstrates a more balanced approach with moderate weights across all criteria resulting in a performance of 6.2156.

Fig. 6: Tree Overlays for Different Grid Sizes on Maze Map.

This balance suggests that using all weighted components synergistically improves the decision making process.

Run 5, which ran a 100 trials allowing a much broader exploration of the weight space, produced the best overall performance. The resulting performance of 6.6032 indicates that allowing more iterations in optimisation helps in discovering more optimal configurations, especially when the parameter space is complex.

The Bayesian optimisation subsystem proved to be an effective tool for tuning the goal selection parameters. The comparative analysis indicates that a balanced configuration, where all three weights contribute in a moderate fashion, tends to yield the best result. The results also highlight the importance of sufficient exploration of the weight space as seen with the improvement between the 30 trial run and the 100 trial run. The performance of the exploration system can be further enhanced by increasing the number of trials to explore more of the weight space, or by enhancing the cost function with better parameters. Ultimately, these findings suggest that careful tuning of the cost function can significantly enhance the system’s capabilities and that Bayesian optimisation is a viable tool in this use case.

VI. CONCLUSION

In simulation both frontier detection methods achieved high coverage, effectively guiding the robot to explore nearly all reachable areas of the test environments. The grid tree based approach proved to be efficient and reliable by incrementally expanding a tree data structure through free space in a grid manner, it quickly evaluated frontier cells with minimal redundant checks. This methods computational overhead remained low and it consistently provided accurate and valid centroid targets until the full environment was explored. The image based approach leverages a trained CNN to recognise frontier regions. This approach was able to detect centroids even in complex or noisy maps by treating frontier detection as an object recognition task. While the image based approach ran faster, it delivered slightly lower exploration completeness. This gap could potentially be closed by retraining the model with more data in the future. Notably, both methods were robust throughout the simulations, the grid tree based approach,

which is deterministic, reliably found new frontiers at each iteration and the image based approach maintained accurate centroid predictions. No critical failure was observed for either method, adding to their reliability in the tested scenarios. Each frontier detection technique offers distinct advantages and consideration for real-world autonomous exploration. The grid tree based method is lightweight and transparent relying only on occupancy grid data and a basic data structure, utilising culling behaviour and parallelises computationally heavy operations. This makes it well suited for deployment on real robots with computationally limited resources and ensures predictable behaviour in diverse environments. In contrast, the image based method introduces a vision centric perspective to frontier detection, which can be advantageous in recognising irregular frontier patterns or filtering out spurious noise. However, deploying this approach in a real robot would require adequate computing hardware and a trained model that generalises well to the robot’s operational setting. Bayesian optimisation to fine tune parameters in a goal selection process was also introduced in this paper. It has proved a valuable tool in further enhancing the exploration algorithm based on quantitative metrics and provides a solid foundation for further research in optimisation methods in robotic exploration. While our evaluation was in realistic simulation, deploying these methods on real robots is an important next step. We expect the grid tree method to transfer well given its low computation, and the CNN would require a robot with a suitable GPU. Real-world tests could validate the robustness of the approach under real sensor noise and dynamics.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Burgard, M. Moors, C. Stachniss, and F. E. Schneider, “Coordinated multi-robot exploration,” *IEEE Trans. Robotics*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 376–386, 2005. doi:10.1109/TRO.2004.839232
- [2] B. Yamauchi, “A frontier-based approach for autonomous exploration,” in *Proc. 1997 IEEE Int. Symp. Computational Intelligence in Robotics and Automation (CIRA)*, 1997, pp. 146–151. doi:10.1109/CIRA.1997.613851
- [3] A. Topiwala, P. Inani, and A. Kathpal, “Frontier Based Exploration for Autonomous Robot,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1806.03581, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1806.03581>
- [4] A. Elfes, “Occupancy Grids: A Stochastic Spatial Representation for Active Robot Perception,” arXiv:1304.1098, 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1304.1098>

- [5] P. Quin, D. D. K. Nguyen, T. L. Vu, A. Alempijevic, and G. Paul, "Approaches for Efficiently Detecting Frontier Cells in Robotics Exploration," *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, vol. 8, 2021, art. 616470. doi:10.3389/frobt.2021.616470
- [6] G. Jocher, "Ultralytics YOLO11," ver. 11.0.0, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>
- [7] Wikipedia contributors, "Bayesian Optimization," Wikipedia, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bayesian_optimization
- [8] P. I. Frazier, "A Tutorial on Bayesian Optimization," arXiv:1807.02811, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.02811>
- [9] scikit-optimize contributors, "scikit-optimize: Sequential model-based optimization with a `scikit-learn` interface," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://scikit-optimize.github.io/>
- [10] Python Software Foundation, "subprocess — Subprocess management," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.python.org/3/library/subprocess.html>
- [11] scikit-learn developers, "sklearn.cluster.DBSCAN — scikit-learn 1.6.1 documentation," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.cluster.DBSCAN.html>
- [12] D. Holz, N. Basilico, F. Amigoni, and S. Behnke, "Evaluating the Efficiency of Frontier-based Exploration Strategies," in *ISR 2010 & ROBOTIK 2010*, 2010, pp. 1–8.